

GST and Economic Growth

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Abstract

Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacture, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level. One of the biggest taxation reforms in India the (GST) is all set to integrate State economies and boost overall growth. Currently, companies and businesses pay lot of indirect taxes such as VAT, service tax, sales tax, rtainment tax, octroi and luxury tax. Once GST is implemented, all these taxes would cease to exist. There would be only one tax, that too at the national level, monitored by the central government. GST is also different in the way it is levied — at the final point of consumption and not at the manufacturing stage. At present, separate tax rates are applied to goods and services. Under GST, there would be only one tax rate for both goods and services. The goods and services Tax will indeed be a further significant improvement towards a comprehensive indirect tax reforms in the country. Integration of goods and services taxation would give India a world class tax system and improve tax collections. It would end distortions of differential treatments of manufacturing and service sector. GST is expected to create a business friendly environment, as price levels and hence inflation rates would come down overtime as a uniform tax rate is applied. It will also improve government’s fiscal health as the tax collection system would become more transparent, making tax evasion difficult. An attempt is made in this paper to study the concept of goods and service tax and its impact on Indian economy. The study also aims to know the advantages and challenges of GST in Indian scenario.

Introduction

GST the biggest tax reform in India founded on the notion of “one nation, one market, one tax” is finally here. The moment that the Indian government was waiting for a decade has finally arrived. The single biggest indirect tax regime has kicked into force, dismantling all the inter-state barriers with respect to trade. The GST rollout, with a single stroke, has converted India into a unified market of 1.3 billion citizens. Fundamentally, the \$2.4-trillion economy is attempting to transform itself by doing away with the internal tariff barriers and subsuming central, state and local taxes into a unified GST. Tax policies play an important role on the economy through their impact on both efficiency and equity. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a vast concept that simplifies the giant tax structure by supporting and enhancing the economic growth of a country. GST is a comprehensive tax levy on manufacturing, sale and consumption of goods and services at a national level.

Under this system, the consumer pays the final tax but an efficient input tax credit system ensures that there is no cascading of taxes- tax on tax paid on inputs that go into manufacture of goods.

In order to avoid the payment of multiple taxes such as excise duty and service tax at Central level and VAT at the State level, GST would unify these taxes and create a uniform market throughout the country. Integration of various taxes into a GST system will bring about an effective cross-utilization of credits.

Salient Features of Proposed Indian GST System

- The power to make laws in respect of supplies in the course of inter-State trade or commerce will be vested only in the Union government. States will have the right to levy GST on intra-State transactions including on services.
- Centre will levy IGST on inter-State supply of goods and services. Import of goods will be subject to basic customs duty and IGST.
- GST defined as any tax on supply of goods and services other than on alcohol for human consumption.
- Central taxes like, Central Excise duty, Additional Excise duty, Service tax, Additional Custom duty and Special Additional duty and State level taxes like, VAT or sales tax, Central Sales tax, Entertainment tax, Entry tax, Purchase tax, Luxury tax and Octroi will subsume in GST.
- Petroleum and petroleum products i.e. crude, high speed diesel, motor spirit, aviation turbine fuel and natural gas shall be subject to the GST on a date to be notified by the GST Council.
- 1% origin based additional tax to be levied on inter-State supply of goods will be non-creditable in GST chain. The revenue from this tax is to be assigned to the Origin State. This tax is proposed to be levied for initial two years or such period as recommended by the GST Council.
- Provision for removing imposition of entry tax / Octroi across India.
- Entertainment tax, imposed by States on movie, theatre, etc will be subsumed in GST, but taxes on entertainment at panchayat, municipality or district level to continue.
- GST may be levied on the sale of newspapers and advertisements and this would give the government's access to substantial incremental revenues.
- Stamp duties, typically imposed on legal agreements by the state, will continue to be levied by the States.
- Administration of GST will be the responsibility of the GST Council, which will be the apex policy making body for GST. Members of GST Council comprised of the Central and State ministers in charge of the finance portfolio.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the concept of Goods and Services Tax (GST) and its impact on Indian Economy.
- To understand how GST will work in India.
- To know the advantages and challenges of GST in Indian context.

GST – How it Works in India?

The GST system is based on the same concept as VAT. Here, set-off is available in respect of taxes paid in the previous level against the GST charged at the time of sale. The GST model has some aspects which are as follows:

Components: GST will be divided into two components, namely, Central Goods and Service Tax and State Goods and Service

Applicability: GST will be applicable to all Goods and Services sold or provided in India, except from the list of exempted goods which fall outside its purview.

Payment: GST will be charged and paid separately in case of Central and State level. Input Tax
Credit: The facility of Input Tax Credit at Central level will only be available in respect of Central Goods and Service tax. In other words, the ITC of Central Goods and Service tax shall not be allowed as a set-off against State Goods and Service tax and vice versa.

Positive Aspects of GST

- The main reason to implement GST is to abolish the cascading effect on tax. A product on which excise duty is paid can also be liable to VAT. Suppose a product A is manufactured in a factory. As soon as it releases from factory, excise duty has to be paid to central government. When the product A is sold in same state then VAT has to be paid to the State Government. Also no credit on excise duty paid can be taken against output VAT. This is termed as cascading effect since double taxes is levied on same product.
- GST will lead to more transparent and neutral manner to raise revenue.
- Implementation of GST will help resolve various issues concerning taxation and logistics with regard to e-commerce business, which has been recording rapid growth in the country, says a study.
- Simplified and cost saving system as procedural cost reduces due to uniform accounting for all types of taxes. Only three type of account; CGST, SGST & IGST have to be maintained.
- GST is structured to simplify the current indirect system. It is a long term strategy leading to a higher output, more employment opportunities and economy boom.
- It is beneficial for both economy and corporations. The reduced tax burden on companies will reduce production cost making exporters more competitive.
- GST will reduce transaction costs for taxpayers through simplified tax compliance.
- It will result in increased tax collections due to wider tax base and better conformity.
- For the Centre and the States: According to experts, by implementing GST, India will gain \$ 15 Billion a year. This is because it will promote more exports, create more employment opportunities and boost growth.
- For individuals and companies: In the GST system, taxes for both Centre and State will be collected at one point of sale. Both will be charge on manufacturing cost. Individuals will be benefited by this as prices are likely to come down. Lower price mean more consumption, more consumption means more production
- The implementation of GST will make industry more competitive through dismantling of the complex indirect tax structure and boost the tax revenue of states and thereby helping in the growth of the companies.

Negative Aspects of GST

At Present, lots of speculations are going as to when the GST will actually be applicable in India. Looking into the political environment of India, it seems that a little more time will be required to ensure that everybody is satisfied. The states are confused as to whether the GST will hamper their revenues. Although the Central Government has assured the states about compensation in case the revenue falls down, still a little mistrust can be a severe draw back. The GST is a very good type of tax. However, for the successful implementation of the same, there are few challenges which have to face to implement GST In India. Following are some of the factors that must be kept in mind about GST

- Firstly, it is really required that all the states implement the GST together and that too at the same rates. Otherwise, it will be really cumbersome for businesses to comply with the provisions of the law. Further, GST will be very advantageous if the rates are same, because in that case taxes will not be a factor in investment location decisions, and people will be able to focus on profitability.

- For smooth functioning, it is important that the GST clearly sets out the taxable event. Presently, the CENVAT credit rules, the Point of Taxation Rules are amended/ introduced for this purpose only. However, the rules should be more refined and free from ambiguity.
- The GST is a destination based tax, not the origin one. In such circumstances, it should be clearly identifiable as to where the goods are going. This shall be difficult in case of services, because it is not easy to identify where a service is provided, thus this should be properly dealt with.
- More awareness about GST and its advantages have to be made, and professionals like us really have to take the onus to assume this responsibility

Conclusion

Tax policies play an important role on the economy through their impact on both efficiency and equity. A good tax system should keep in view issues of income distribution and, at the same time, also endeavour to generate tax revenues to support government expenditure on public services and infrastructure development. The ongoing tax reforms on moving to a goods and services tax would impact the national economy, International trade, firms and the consumers There has been a good deal of criticism as well as appraisal of the proposed Goods and Services Tax regime. It is considered to be a major improvement over the pre-existing central excise duty at the national level and the sales tax system at the state level, the new tax will be a further significant breakthrough and the next logical step towards a comprehensive indirect tax reform in the country. GST is not simply VAT plus service tax, but a major improvement over the previous system of VAT and disjointed services tax – a justified step forward. A single rate would help maintain simplicity and transparency by treating all goods and services as equal without giving special treatment to some ‘special’ goods and/or services. This will reduce litigation on classification issues. It is also expected that implementation of GST in the Indian framework will lead to commercial benefits which were untouched by the VAT system and would essentially lead to economic development. Hence GST may usher in the possibility of a collective gain for industry, trade, agriculture and common consumers as well as for the Central Government and the State Government. Sooner or later, the GST will surely knock the doors of India. And when that happens, we as future torch bearers of the profession are required to be prepared and fully equipped with our knowledge regarding GST. Forewarned is forearmed. Thus, must be ready to deal with GST and many other changes that are going to take place in India. Slowly, India shall move to join the world wide standards in taxation, corporate laws and managerial practices and be among the leaders in these fields.

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Table Corporates’ agreement on Implementation of the GST

Opinion	Frequency Percent	Frequency Count
Strongly Agree	31.3%	47
Agree	46.7%	70
Neither Agree nor Disagree	16.0%	24
Disagree	4.7%	7
Strongly Disagree	1.3%	2
Total	100%	150

The GST is expected to unify the fragmented market in India and reduce cascading impact. In this connection, the opinion was gathered from the respondents on competitiveness of GST. Table 1 reveals that, 31.3% of the respondents strongly agreed and 46.7% of the respondents agreed that, “implementation of the proposed Goods and Services Tax (GST) would make their organization and industry more competitive”. While, 16% of the respondents were undecided, 4.7% and 1.3% of the respondents were disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively, with the statement made. In general, the overall picture generates the hope that, the GST will get good support from the majority of business & industrial community in India in the global environment.

Review of literature

Shilpa Parkhi: “Goods and service tax: The changing face of economy.” And explained the concept of goods and service to be implemented in India and the changing face of Indian Taxation and helps in understanding the present structure of induced taxes, such as central sales tax, service tax etc. and the method of levy and collection of Goods and service tax.

Nitin Kumar (2014 studied): Goods and service tax in India: Away forward and explained the background of GST, silent features, advantages and the impact of GST in the tax scenario in India.

Dr.R.Vasanthgopal (2011 studied): “GST in India: A Big Leap in the Indirect Taxation System” and found that the positive impacts are dependent on a neural and rational design of the GST, balancing the conflicting interests of various stakeholders, full political commitment for a fundamental tax reforms with a constitutional amendment, the method.

Nishitha Gupta (2014 studied): In her study stated that implementation of GST in the Indian framework will lead to commercial benefits which were untouched by the VAT system and would essentially lead to economic development. Hence GST may usher in the possibility of a collective gain for industry, trade, agriculture and common consumers as well as for the central government and state government.